

JURISPRUDENCE

THE CATEGORY OF INITIAL LETTERS WHICH ARE THE SPECIAL SIGNS OF LINES

Abbasov E.,

Senior lecturer of the chair "Legal studies" of NSU

Aliyev E.,

Lecturer of the chair "Legal studies" of NSU

Aliyev H.

Senior lecturer of the chair "Legal studies" of NSU

Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan

Abstract

The article elaborates the special signs included in the category of signs of the line, their description and the criteria for evaluating the signs. In a group of words of manuscript texts, there are line signs that reflect the features of writing initial letters. Although the main focus here is on capital letters, line letters have not been left out of the study. In the study of calligraphy, how or in what form the beginning and end of the words are executed has been one of the main principles that have been taken into consideration. In the article, the natural reasons for this have been investigated and explained. Also, researches and experiments conducted in the world experience in this direction were examined and references were made.

Keywords: special sign, initials, category of signs, research methodology, evaluation of signs

In a group of words of manuscript texts, there are line signs that reflect the features of writing initial letters. Here, along with initial letters, line letters are also considered. The writing of the beginnings and ends of words has undoubtedly been one of the issues of interest for the study of the line. Initial characters often include features that line characters do not. There is a natural reason for this. The first letters have initials, and the last letters have the last. In handwritten texts, the beginning and end of the word can already be executed with different writing speed and pressure. During the execution of the texts, the sizes of the letters are often different. The size of initial letters in handwritten texts is characterized as follows:

Description of the sign: it is especially noticeable when the size of the initial letters differs from the average size of the letters within the line;

Sign evaluation: the average size of the initial letters should be compared with the average size of the letters within the line when determining the average size. However, the fact that other dimensions of the line fall into the interval is not as important as in the assessment of alignment. A difference of 1-2 mm in the size of the letters is enough during the study. The average size of the initial letters of the word falls into another interval when the line differs significantly from the average size of the letters. In this case, it is necessary to accept the numerical value of the sign equal to 1. A number of characteristics of line symbols are reflected in table 1 below [1, p.41-43].

Table 1.

Characteristics of the line signs

Characteristics	Value	Explanations
Level	Macro-sign	The size of the letters is also a macro-sign
Frequency	Constant	It is possible to evaluate according to each text
Structure	Dependent	Initial sign-the size of letters
Measurement	Selected	Comparison model of averages. One of the values is chosen
Expressiveness	Polychotomic	Line sign has 3 meanings
Additiveness	No	Line sign may be considered additive, because the values meet all criteria. But as one value is chosen, it is not correct formally.
Basis of sign	Initial letters, line letters in words	
Weight of the sign	0.1	

Line signs have the following characteristics:

1. Initial letters are larger than inline letters.
2. Initial letters are smaller than inline letters.
3. Initial letters do not differ in size from inline letters.

These mentioned symptoms are more typical. The inclination of capital letters is evaluated by describing it as follows:

Description of the sign: when the tendency of the initial letters is different from the tendency of the letters

within the line, the frequency of occurrence of the signs is less;

Sign evaluation: the size of capitalization bias is compared with the average size of inline letters bias. Letter sizes belong to another category when the average size of the inclination of the initial letters differs greatly from the inclination of the letters within the line. At this time, the value of the size of those signs, that is, the level, is considered equal to 1. The characteristics of the size of the line signs are explained in table 2 below[2, p.37-40].

Table 2

Characteristics of the line signs

Characteristics	Value	Explanations
Level	Macro-sign	Bias is a macro-sign
Frequency	Constant	It is possible to evaluate according to each text
Structure	Dependent	Initial sign-bias
Measurement	Selected	Comparison model of averages
Expressiveness	Polychotomic	Sign expresses 6 meanings
Additiveness	No	The sign may be considered additive because values meet all criteria
Basis of the sign	Initial letters, line letters in words	
Weight of the sign	0.1	

The given line marks mean the following.

1. Initial letters have a different bias than inline letters.

This means that the direction of bias changes in initial letters. Here the difference is much stronger. If inlines are right-leaning, initials must be straight or left-leaning.

2. Initial letters have a stronger right bias.
3. Initial letters have a weaker right bias.
4. Initial letters have a stronger left bias.
5. Initial letters have a weaker left bias.
6. Initial letters tend to be indented.

One of the more frequent cases in handwritten texts is the writing of the initial letters adjacent to the following letters. The spelling of initial letters adjacent to inline letters is noted as follows:

Description of the sign: when all the letters in the handwritten text are connected, it is noticeable whether the initials are written together or separately. In an unrelated line, the initials will be indistinguishable from the rest. However, in an unconnected line, the case where only initial letters are combined with the letter that follows them is practically not found.

Sign evaluation: at the beginning of the study, it is calculated how many initial letters are executed in connection with the next letter or word and how many initial letters are executed without connection. The corresponding ratio of the total number of initials is based on the value of both levels of the sign. Therefore, in the conducted research, not only initial letters, but also inline letters should be considered. The characteristics of the initial letters are given in table 3 below[1, p.45-52].

Table 3

Characteristics of line signs

Characteristics	Value	Explanations
Level	Macro-sign	Coherence of the line as an initial sign is a macro-sign
Frequency	Facultative	Only coherent line is explored
Structure	Dependent	Initial sign- coherence of the line
Measurement	Assessed	Model of occurrence frequency
Expressiveness	Dichotomic	The sign has two opposite meanings
Additiveness	Additive	On the basis of occurrence frequency, it is possible to determine the level of both values. The total value of these signs equals 1
Basis of the sign	Initial letters in words, (line)	
Weight of the sign	0.1	

The meanings of the given line signs.

1. The initials are coherent;
2. It is typical for coherent executed lines;
3. Initial letters are not combined with other letters

of the word.

Description of the sign: the difference between the shape of the capital letters and the shape of the inner letters is considered important for the study. The characteristics of the shape and direction of the initials are studied in the conducted research. These features are mainly expressed in comparison with the middle zone. Separate signs are defined for above-line and below-line zones. An important part of the study is that it is the signs that differ from the letters within the line that are analyzed. If the mentioned are general characteristics, then those symptoms are related to general symptoms. The issue that we are trying to investigate in the article covers the category of initials that are characteristic of the special features of the line.

Evaluation of the sign: if the evaluation of the prepared expert opinions is carried out by the judicial and investigative bodies, then in the conducted research, the process of evaluation of the signs is reflected in the synthesis part of the opinion by the expert. At the threshold of the study, the pattern of the formal frequency of signs is almost inconsistent, so very rarely the form differs for all letters. From this point of view, as a rule, one or two different letters can be observed at the beginning of the word in the text. In such a study, the last letters of the word are not so important for the study. Because often the performance characteristics of those letters have the writing characteristics of line letters. The initials are divided into two main parts [3, p.73-77].

Here, the first part of the letter, i.e. the 1st element, remains free, and the second part is often combined with the letters of the following line. The selection of traits in the research can be carried out in a vertical direction. These signs include the uppercase letters of the Latin alphabet "A", "M", "V", especially the lowercase letters of the Cyrillic alphabet "т", "ш", "щ" or the lowercase letters of the Latin alphabet "m", "v", "n". " and other letters can be selected according to their size in the vertical direction. Here, a difference can be observed according to the degree of pressing force. Even other distinguishing features of the first part of the letter may be possible as follows.

1. Initial (capital) letters are tall and narrow.

The beginning, especially the capital letters, are higher and narrower than the letters after them.

2. The form of the initial (capital) letters is executed in a complex or complicated way.

The execution of capital letters in a complex form can be judged by its fundamental difference from line letters. It should be noted that only line letters are examined and compared here [4, p.78-83].

3. The initial (capital) letters are executed in a braided manner.

Line letters executed after capital letters are not executed with a different form and direction from the capital letters. Therefore, in the study, it is necessary to pay attention only to those letters for which, in principle, it is possible to find more braided forms. All this is necessary to compare the special signs in the letters found within the word in the text.

In addition to capital letters, attention should also be paid to whether or not the inclination is changed in the last letters of the word. Although the direction of change does not play a major role here, it is considered one of the necessary variables in the research.

If the last letters in a word have the specified property, it is significant. A sign such as a change in pressure can be found quite often. However, regularity is not significant for change in inclination. In the word, some last letters can differ on one side, and others on the other side. Importantly, they are different from in-line letters. [5, p.65-67].

The direction of inclination of the last letters in the word is not necessarily changed. However, the signs must fall into the other group in order to talk about the difference in susceptibility. Therefore, it is important to evaluate the inclination of the whole line, except for the last letters of the word.

References

1. Чернов Ю.Г Психологический анализ почерка: М.: Гнезис, 2011, 464 с.
2. Щеголев И, Чернов Ю. Графология XXI века. СПб.: Питер, 2008.
3. Гольдберг И. Психология почерка. М.: АСТ, 2008.
4. Pfanne H. Lehrbuch der Graphologie. Berlin, 1961, s.78-83.
5. Klages L. Handschrift und Charakter. Leipzig, 1941, 254 s.